

Effect of Two-Track Methods and Syntactic Skills on Grade Five Pupils

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the effect of Two-Track Methods on Grade Five pupils and to quantify the impact of Syntactic Skills on their reading knowledge acquisition. Grounded in Piaget’s theory (1966) which describes the interaction between environmental information and individual cognition leading to internalized learning structures, the research adopted a constructivist framework. Conducted at Dawis Elementary School, Division of Digos City, Davao Del Sur, the study involved 60 Grade Five learners, with 26 in the control group (Section A) and 34 in the experimental group (Section B). Both groups were homogeneous, possessing identical grades, and the study utilized a non-random assignment of subjects. The research revealed that the implementation of the Two-Track Method significantly enhanced the syntactic skills of Grade Five pupils. Additionally, there was a notable difference in the post-test scores between the control and experimental groups, indicating the efficacy of the Two-Track Method in improving syntactic skills.

KEY WORDS

1. Two-track methods. 2. Syntactic skills.

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1. Introduction

The two-track method in education refers to a system where students are grouped into two separate tracks or pathways based on their academic abilities, interests, or needs. This method aims to provide tailored instruction and support to students, allowing them to progress at a pace and level that best suits their individual learning requirements. Effective language education programs focus on both meaning and accuracy to help students gain fluency and confidence in listening, speaking, reading and writing their home language and the school language as well as other languages they learn. The two-track method for introducing L1 literacy emphasizes “meaning” (focus on whole texts) and “accuracy”² (focus on word identification). Since activities in both tracks include some meaning and some accuracy, the distinction is on the main focus of activities in each one (Casey et.al., 2020). The teacher should not read anything to the students that they can read themselves. In a normal Accuracy Track lesson, the only thing that is new is the letter/sound that is introduced in the key word. All the other words and sentences use letters that the students have already learned. Students feel encouraged when they read words and sentences without the teacher’s help. The benefits of building children’s confidence in reading and writing their L1 early in their education are so important that it is worth

devoting the class time needed to do it well. That means Meaning Track and Accuracy Track each day. In a two-track system, educators differentiate instruction to meet the diverse needs of students in each track. This may involve varying the pace, content, or instructional strategies to accommodate different learning styles and abilities (Gamoran and Berends, 2020).

One track typically consists of students who demonstrate advanced skills and abilities in certain subjects. These students may be offered accelerated coursework or enrichment activities to challenge them and further develop their talents. The other track is designed for students who may require additional support or remediation to master grade-level content. Teachers in this track provide targeted interventions, scaffolded instruction, and extra practice to help students build foundational skills and bridge learning gaps (Gamoran, 2022). Syntactic skills refer to the ability to understand and apply the rules governing the structure of language, particularly at the level of sentences and phrases. These skills are fundamental to communication and language comprehension, as they enable individuals to construct grammatically correct sentences, understand the meaning of written or spoken language, and effectively convey their thoughts and ideas to others. Here are some key aspects of syntactic skills (Cain and Oakhill, 2020). Syntactic skills develop gradually over time through exposure to language and explicit instruction in grammar and syntax. As individuals engage with language through reading, writing, speaking, and listening, they refine their syntactic skills and become more proficient communicators. Syntactic skills are fundamental to language proficiency and play a crucial role in various aspects of communication, including reading, writing, speaking, and listening. Developing strong syntactic skills enhances individuals' ability to express themselves clearly and understand others' messages accurately, contributing to effective communi-

cation and successful interpersonal interactions (Carlisle, 2024). The unique contribution of vocabulary knowledge to reading comprehension has been consistently established in a variety of factor analytic, correlational, and experimental studies as one of the best predictors of reading comprehension among school-aged children at the elementary, middle school, high school, and college levels. For instance, in a factor analytic study aimed at determining the basic skills underlying reading comprehension among a large group of college freshmen, Davis (2020) found that word knowledge had a factor loading of 80 (Bowey and Patel, 2020). In the Division of Digos City particularly in Dawis Elementary School the same problem is encountered on the poor acquisition skills among early graders the researcher being a reading teacher explores on the effectiveness of track-methods on the syntactic skills of the young learners. Hence, this study.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

*1.1.1. Two-Track Method—*The two-track method in education involves organizing students into distinct groups based on their academic abilities, interests, or needs, allowing for tailored instruction. At the beginning of the academic term, students undergo assessments to determine their proficiency levels. They are then placed into either a higher track for advanced skills or a lower track for those needing additional support (Hallinan 2024). This method aims to meet the diverse needs of learners, ensuring better academic outcomes by providing differentiated instruction (Hoffer and Moore 2019).

The two-track method helps close achievement gaps by providing targeted support to students at risk of falling behind, thus promoting equity and inclusivity in education (Zittleman and Sadker 2020). It fosters a supportive and collaborative learning environment, boosting student confidence and encouraging peer learning (Oakes 2021). With smaller, homogeneous

groups, teachers can better target their instruction, leading to increased effectiveness and job satisfaction (Oakes et al. 2024). The method relies on data-driven assessments and progress monitoring to inform instructional decisions, ensuring that strategies are effective and responsive to students' needs (Slavin 2020).

However, ability grouping can perpetuate educational inequalities, stigmatize students, and limit opportunities for advancement (Gamoran and Berends 2020). Teachers' expectations may vary based on the track, influencing the quality of instruction and support (Hoffer and Moore 2019). The track method can also impact social dynamics, limiting interactions among students of diverse backgrounds (Gamoran 2022).

1.1.2. Syntactic Skills—Syntactic skills involve understanding grammatical rules, sentence structure, and word order. Mastery of these rules allows individuals to construct grammatically correct sentences, facilitating clear communication (Baumann et al. 2023). Strong syntactic skills enhance language comprehension, enabling individuals to parse sentences accurately and extract meaning from written or spoken language (Blackmore 2020). Developing these skills in students improves reading comprehension, writing skills, and overall language proficiency (Bowey and Patel 2020).

Exposure to diverse linguistic patterns helps expand vocabulary and foster higher-order thinking skills such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation (Cain 2020). Syntactic skills are crucial for standardized tests and academic success across various subjects (Chall et al. 2020). They also contribute to self-confidence in language-rich environments, positively impacting motivation and engagement (Abrahamsen and Shelton 2019).

While essential for language proficiency, an excessive focus on syntactic accuracy may inhibit fluency and natural communication skills (Beers and Nagy 2020). Overemphasis on gram-

matical correctness might limit the development of vocabulary and comprehension strategies (Clark and Hecht 2020). Nonetheless, syntactic skills play a significant role in effective communication, critical thinking, and cross-linguistic transfer (Duin and Graves 2017; Fisher and Frey 2023).

Investing in the development of syntactic skills enhances language proficiency, empowering individuals to succeed in diverse personal, academic, and professional contexts (Farah et al. 2020).

1.2. Synthesis—The above-stated review of significant literatures discussed the prevalence of the problem under study in different context. They also discussed methodologies on how the current issue is solved. There are findings and recommendations presented to resolve the problem. These literatures backed up the occurrence of the problem and different localities present solutions. They also serve as roadmap to guide the researcher in the conduct of the study.

1.3. Theoretical Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on the theory of Piaget (1966) who articulated mechanisms by which information from the environment and ideas from the individual interact and result in internalized structures developed by learners. Constructivism is the theory that says learners construct knowledge rather than just passively take in information. As people experience the world and reflect upon those experiences, they build their own representations and incorporate new information into their pre-existing knowledge (schemas). This is supported by Krashen (1982) who explained that Acquisition Learning involves the subconscious acceptance of knowledge where information is stored in the brain through the use of communication. Krashen (1982) emphasizes the innate subconscious process involved when acquiring a new language, rather than emphasizing conscious processes such as memorizing explicit grammar rules.

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study.

This theory also focuses on the importance of comprehensible input, or language content that can be understood by the learner while remaining one step above the learner’s language ability, in order to encourage critical thinking and new learning.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—This study seeks to determine the Effect of Two-Track Methods on Grade Five Pupils. Eventually, it also seeks to determine the magnitude of effect of Syntactic Skills on the reading knowledge acquisition of grade five pupils. Moreover, it seeks answer to the following sub-problems:

- (1) What is the pre-test scores of the grade five learners both from controlled and experimental groups?
- (2) What is the pre-test scores of the grade five learners both from controlled and experimental groups?
- (3) Is there a significant difference on the post test scores of the grade five learners from controlled and experimental groups?
- (4) What is the magnitude of effect of the Two-Track Methods and Syntactic Skills on Grade Five Pupils?

1.5. Null Hypothesis—The null hypothesis in this study will be tested at 0.05 level of significance. H01. The two-track method and syntactic skills on grade pupils has no effect on the academic performance of the grade five learners.

1.6. Significant of the Study—The results and findings of this study will be beneficial to the following: DEpEd. The Department of Education should know the results and findings of this study in order for them to create a policy that would consider Two-Track Methods and Syntactic Skills on Grade Five Pupils as an integral part of instruction in schools. Besides, the department will conduct a reorientation for all school leaders on the mechanics on the conduct

of Two-Track Methods and Syntactic Skills on Grade Five Pupils. School Heads. Being the manager in school, the school head needs to know the results and findings of this study Two-Track Methods and Syntactic Skills on Grade Five Pupils for them to initiate school-based program that would strengthen the implementation of this study. Teachers. The teachers should have extended extra miles by conducting Two-Track Methods and Syntactic Skills on Grade Five Pupils. Learner can be guided futher if teacher give futher instruction on the activity. Future Researchers. The results and findings of this study will give insights to fu-

ture researchers to the importance of Two-Track Methods and Syntactic Skills on Grade Five Pupils as an advantage on the part of the learners. . To make the study comprehensive the following terms are conceptually define operational. Two-Track Methods and Syntactic Skills refer to the strategy used by the teacher where he teaches first literature before he moves to grammar. The grammar focus will taken from the story or selection that he presented earlier. The learner simply go back to the selection where the grammar focus is found. This is easier way for learners to learn grammar.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. *Research Design*—This study makes use of the quasi experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good

design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the controlled group
- 04 Posttest of the controlled group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study conducted in Dawis Elementary School, Division of Digos City, Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study are the 60 grade five learners – 26 are from section A which is the controlled group and 34 are from section B which is the exper-

imental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

Since it is pandemic time, the experiment is conducted based on the mechanics of Two-Track Methods.

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	No. of Pupils	
1	Section A	26
2	Section B	34
Total		60

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same time meet the learners in face to face but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learners with the permission of parents during face to face sessions for a follow up of what has been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 30 –item

test is eventually determine the academic performance of the research subjects. The pretest is administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest will be very helpful to assess the syntactic skills of grade five learners. On the hand, post test is administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the syntactic skills of grade five learners, the following continuum will be used based on DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Dr. Melanie P. Estacio, CESO VI, the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Digos City and to the school principal concerned. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the DepED Schools Division Superintendent and to the principal of Dawis Elementary School, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Dawis Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pre-test to both controlled and experimental class and eventually

commences her experiment in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer post-test to both sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the syntactic skills of the subjects from controlled and experimental groups in pre-test and post-test. t-test for uncorrelated samples was used to test the significance of difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores in the experimental and controlled groups. Eta square was used to measure the magnitude of effect of Two-Track Methods on the Syntactic Skills of Grade Five learners.

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

3.1. *Pre-Test Score of Learners*—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade five pupils. The controlled group got the mean of 13.86 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 14.79 or Beginning.

Table 1: Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group (Pre-test)	26	13.86	Beginning (55.44)
Experimental Group (Pre-test)	34	14.79	Beginning (59.16)

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Abrahamsen and Shelton (2019) who said that syntactic skills are transferable across different subjects and disciplines. Students who possess strong syntac-

tic skills can apply them in various academic contexts, including math, science, social studies, and beyond, leading to greater overall academic achievement. As students master syntactic skills, they become more confident in their ability to navigate and communicate effectively in language-rich environments. This increased self-confidence can positively impact their motivation, engagement, and overall attitude towards learning. The two-track method in education involves organizing students into two distinct groups or tracks based on their academic abilities, interests, or needs. This approach allows educators to provide differentiated instruction and support tailored to the diverse learning re-

quirements of students. At the beginning of a school year or academic term, students undergo assessments to determine their proficiency levels in key subjects. Based on the assessment results, students are placed into one of two tracks: a higher track for students who demonstrate advanced skills and readiness, and a lower track for students who may require additional support or remediation (Hallinan, 2024).

3.2. *Post-Test Score of Pupils*—Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade five learners. The controlled group got the mean of 20.47 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 22.13 or Approaching Proficiency.

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Post-test	26	20.47	81.88	Developing
Experimental Group				
Post-test	34	22.13	88.52	Approaching Proficiency

It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 7.34 from a mean rating of 14.79 to 22.13. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Cain (2020) who cited that Syntactic skills enable students to express themselves more clearly and effectively in both spoken and written communication. They can convey their thoughts, ideas, and arguments with precision, leading to more successful interactions in various social and academic settings. Developing syntactic skills often involves exposure to a wide range of vocabulary. As students encounter and engage with diverse sentence structures and language patterns, they also expand their vocabulary, further enhancing their

language proficiency. In a two-track system, students who require additional support or enrichment can receive more targeted assistance. Teachers can provide personalized interventions, remediation, or extension activities to help students succeed academically. This individualized support helps address learning gaps and challenges, promoting greater academic growth and achievement. Implementing a two-track method can promote greater equity and inclusivity within the classroom. By addressing the diverse learning needs of students, schools can ensure that all students have access to quality education and opportunities for academic success. This helps reduce achievement gaps and promote fairness in education (Malone and Malone, 2017).

3.3. *Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score*—Table 3 shows

the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.34 with a p-value of .0326 which is lesser than .05 level of signif-

icance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade five pupils.

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	38	-5.34	.0326	Significant

This implies that the used of two-track methods in teaching grade five have contributed the effectiveness in enhancing the syntactic skills which is revealed by the scores of the five learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Chall et.al (2020) who said that analyzing the structure of sentences and paragraphs requires students to think critically about the relationships between words and phrases. This fosters higher-order thinking skills such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation, which are essential for academic success in various subjects. Many standardized tests, including state assessments and college entrance exams, assess students' syntactic skills through reading comprehension and writing tasks. By developing strong syntactic skills, grade five pupils are better prepared to excel on these assessments and demonstrate their academic proficiency. The two-track method relies on data-driven assessments and progress monitoring to inform instructional de-

isions. By regularly assessing student progress and adjusting instruction based on their needs, educators can make informed decisions that support student learning and growth. Regular progress monitoring ensures that instructional strategies are effective and responsive to the changing needs of students over time. It offers a structured approach to meeting the diverse needs of students and promoting academic success. By providing differentiated instruction, individualized support, and challenging opportunities, the two-track method helps ensure that all students have the opportunity to achieve their full potential (Slavin, 2017).

3.4. *Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade V Pupils* —Table 4 highlights the test of oral language development programs on the reading fluency of grade five learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.447 which signifies large effect.

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade V Pupils

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
60	-4.46	0.447	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in developing syntactic skills especially that are integral to language acquisition, cognitive development, and effective commu-

nication which is essential for grade 5 learners as they continue to develop their language abilities and literacy skills. Two-track system allows individuals to comprehend and internalize

syntactic structures through exposure to spoken and written language. Receptive language skills involve the ability to understand the meaning conveyed by others through listening or reading. By immersing learners in rich linguistic environments, whether through conversations, storytelling, or reading materials, they develop an intuitive grasp of syntax and grammar. Through repeated exposure to diverse linguistic patterns and sentence structures, individuals gradually internalize the rules and conventions of language, laying the foundation for proficient comprehension (Malone and Malone, 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of two-track methods on the syntactic skills of grade five pupils. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Dawis Elementary School, Division of Digos City. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade five pupils – 26 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 34 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of two-track method has increased the syntactic skills of grade five pupils. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade five pupils both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching Proficiency level.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching grade five students should used two-track method as a strategy that would further develop syntactic skills of the students in order to make the teaching meaningful. Implementing teaching strategies tailored to the needs of diverse learners, enables individuals to comprehend and generate language effectively, facilitating communication, cognitive growth, and linguistic flexibility. The school heads should promote the use of two-track method as a strategy that would enhance the syntactic skills as it is revealed in the study that it is effective especially on subjects that involve the ability to generate spoken or written language to convey thoughts, ideas, and information. A school policy about the utilization of two-track method can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demoteach during LAC session using two-track method as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of two-track method as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

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